

Metal ions in environment and biology[†]

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The intimate links between the distribution of metals in the environment and the role of metal ions for life processes are well recognized nowadays; this holds for both the essential as well as the 'deleterious' metals¹. Indeed, many probably have heard the common and somewhat sarcastic statement, popular among students when talking about their elderly teachers, that they have ... "silver in the hair, gold in the teeth and lead in the bones". Strange as it may seem at first sight, all three mentioned metals can have an effect on living systems :

Silver and its salts have antibacterial properties and are used as disinfectants due to their germicidal effects^{2,3}. For example, silver nitrate (AgNO₃) in diluted solution is administered to the eyes of newborn as a prophylactic agent against gonorrhoeal infections^{2,4}.

Gold compounds, like Auranofin, (2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-acetyl-1-thio- β -D-glucopyranosido-*S*)triethylphosphine-gold(I) (Fig. 1)^{4,5}, are applied as oral drugs against rheumatoid arthritis^{5,6}. Of course, today it is widely known that many other metal-containing compounds are used in medicine^{4,7}, such as Cisplatin, *cis*-(NH₃)₂PtCl₂, which is successfully employed worldwide as an anticancer drug⁸⁻¹⁰, or lithium carbonate, which is given to patients with certain mental disorders¹¹⁻¹³.

Lead is one of the oldest metals known to man and its toxicity was recorded already by Greek and Arab scholars¹⁴. It was known to the early Egyptians, it was mined in Spain as early as 2000 B.C. and there is a statue made of lead in the British Museum that was crafted before 3800 B.C.¹⁵. Lead may enter the environment at any point during mining, melting and refining, manufacturing processes, and the use of lead-containing products^{15,16}. It is transported in the ecosystem by precipitation from the atmosphere to soil and water, uptake by plants and animals, and reentry to the atmosphere; hence, there is a biogeochemical cycle, which indeed exists for all metals¹⁷.

Inputs of natural lead to the ecosystem are mainly from

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of the gold drug Auranofin⁵

geological erosion, however, the most important inputs in industrialized areas of the world are from anthropogenic sources. Atmospheric lead and lead in food are the two major routes of exposure for the general population^{15,16}. Lead interferes with the metabolism and action of essential metals, particularly Ca, Fe and Zn. Pb²⁺ can act as an effective substitute^{15,18} for Ca²⁺ (the radii are 112 and 129 pm for Ca²⁺ and Pb²⁺, respectively¹⁴, for coordination number 8). Lead accumulates in bone, and the skeleton contains approximately 95% of the body burden of lead¹⁶; it is harmful mainly through its neurotoxicological effects^{15,16}. The indicated interdependency between lead and other metals is well known and exists for many metals, like e.g. between copper and zinc or cadmium and zinc. In Fig. 2 some of these interdependencies are summarized with an emphasis on those involving lead¹⁸; evidently, toxicity of lead is worse with a calcium deficiency. Some of the relevant chemistry of Pb²⁺ was recently discussed¹⁹.

Some environmental considerations

Pictures of a snow-topped mountain and a lake in front in brilliant sunshine, as they often appear in calendars, evoke the impression not only of a beautiful but also a clean environment. However, such an environment is not as clean as many people like to think it is, in fact, it never was due to the natural turnover of the elements^{17,20}. For example, in preindustrial times around 1890, approximately eight megamoles, i.e. about 1600 tons, of atmospheric mercury were turned around per year in the global mercury cycle involving the sea and land as well^{21,22}. In modern times,

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Fig. 2. Interdependencies among 30 elements in mammals; those involving Pb are emphasized by larger prints. An arrow from element A \rightarrow B indicates that administration of element A may reduce toxicity due to element B, low levels of element A may heighten the toxicity of element B, or high levels of element B may inhibit salutary effects of element A. Adapted from Ref. 18 with the permission of the author, Prof. Dr. R. Bruce Martin (University of Virginia, Charlottesville), and the publisher, Marcel Dekker, Inc. (New York).

around 1990, the amount of mercury involved in the global cycle had approximately tripled due to human activities. Hence, the amount in the atmosphere increased to about 25 megamoles (corresponding to ca. 5000 tons)^{21,22}. Since this has been recognized, steps are undertaken to reduce the mercury burden worldwide.

Mercury has been known to mankind for a long time²³ and the process of gold amalgamation for gold recovery²⁴ has been applied for at least 2000 years. Previously, mercury and its compounds were employed medicinally for centuries, like mercury sulfide as a remedy for skin and eye complaints, organomercurials (like mercurochrome or thiomersal) as disinfectants, methoxymethylmercury as diuretic, or skin-lightening creams containing ammoniated mercury as cosmetics²⁵.

Mercury is one of the most toxic metals; it is toxic in every form, but depending on the compound the degree of toxicity²⁵ and the critical target organ vary; e.g. sublimate (HgCl_2) initially affects the gastrointestinal mucous membrane followed later by renal failure²⁵, whereas methylmercury damages especially the nervous system²⁶. Mercury is not known to be essential for any metabolic process, yet it is readily accumulated by most organisms²³.

As indicated already above, there is a global cycling of all metals involving land, rivers, oceans and the atmosphere¹⁷, and indeed, atmospheric concentrations of many metals have been measured. For example, the atmospheric concentrations over Europe (given in ng/m^3)¹⁷ are 1200 for Zn, 600 for Al, 340 for Cu and 120 for Pb; the concentration of Fe is usually considered as being about 1/3 of that of Al²⁷. This means, one of the metals also significantly trans-

ported by the atmosphere is iron. It is the fourth most abundant element in the Earth's crust, yet it is present only at ultra-trace concentrations in seawater²⁷.

In this context it is interesting to note that seasonal cycles of phytoplankton abundance are visible features in many parts of the ocean²⁷. Increased solar radiation in Spring creates ideal growth conditions for phytoplankton by increasing the amount and rate of photosynthesis, i.e. the phytoplankton is 'blooming'²⁷. However, in a few regions of the sea, particularly the Equatorial Pacific, the Subarctic Pacific and the Southern Ocean around Antarctica, standing stocks of phytoplankton are always low despite the fact that the nutrients nitrate and phosphate remain at measurable concentrations throughout the year. This has led to the hypothesis²⁷ that iron is the limiting nutrient and indeed, iron fertilization experiments (large patches of surface water were enriched with ferrous sulfate)^{28,29} confirmed this hypothesis²⁷. In agreement with this is also the fact that the calculated flux³⁰ of total iron from the atmosphere to the sea is low in the mentioned ocean parts²⁷.

The above observations have led to considerations on the possible role of iron as a global limiting nutrient²⁷: Is there an intimate link between the global cycle of carbon, or more precisely, the CO_2 concentration in the atmosphere and the inputs and concentrations of iron in the ocean?

One approach to the question of the global role of iron in primary biota production, i.e. CO_2 fixation, is to study the history of the atmosphere and oceans as recorded in polar ice²⁷. Hence, the iron concentration as a function of depth was measured in an Antarctic ice core as was the CO_2 concentration of air trapped in the ice as a function of the age of the ice³¹. One finds that during glacial times the biological CO_2 pump was especially effective and this is explained by the much drier and stormier weather that is thought to have occurred during Ice Ages²⁷. The strong anticorrelation between CO_2 and dust content in the ice is the basis of the so-called 'paleo-iron hypothesis' according to which increased atmospheric inputs of iron to the oceans resulted in higher oceanic primary production and a greater efficiency of the biological CO_2 pump during glacial times. For example, during the last Ice Age (about 18000 years ago) there was a 70-ppm decrease²⁷ in atmospheric CO_2 . These variations in atmospheric CO_2 are presently in the focus of intense research³².

The elements of life

What has determined which of the elements are important for biological systems? It appears that this was largely their availability. The outermost part of the lithosphere, in-

cluding the oceans, the biosphere and the atmosphere, consists of 13 elements which occur in more than 0.1% (weight)^{33,34}; these are O (50.50), Si (27.50), Al (7.30), Fe (3.38), Ca (2.79), K (2.58), Na (2.19), Mg (1.29), H (1.02), Ti (0.43), N (0.33), Cl (0.19) and C (0.12) and together they constitute 99.62%. These 13 elements are followed by another eight, namely, P, F, Mn, S, Ba, Sr, Zn and Rb, which occur in weight percentages of 0.01 or larger and encompass together^{33,34} another 0.35%. Hence, the mentioned 21 elements constitute in total 99.97% of the Earth's crust, leaving only 0.03% for the other 71 elements of the traditional Periodic Table. To the mentioned 21 elements belong seven non-metals (O, H, N, Cl, C, P, S) and four main group metals (Ca, K, Na, Mg) as well as three transition metals (Fe, Mn, Zn) and without these plant and animal life is not possible. In other words, during the evolution of life, those elements were employed which occurred in large quantities and which were easily accessible¹⁸.

It is interesting to consider in this context the abundance of the elements in a human body (wet weight)³⁵: The atom percentages are 62.8% for H, 25.4% for O, 9.4% for C and 1.4% for N, and together they amount already to 99.0%. The seven elements, Na, K, Ca, Mg, P, S and Cl, constitute another 0.9%. Hence, besides these eleven elements, which are absolutely essential, only about 0.1% remain³⁵ for all the other elements, including ten which are required by most biological systems, namely, Mn, Fe and Zn, which were mentioned also before in the context of the Earth's crust, as well as Co, Ni, Cu, Mo, B, Si and Se. Yet, another seven elements are or appear also to be essential for life³⁵: V, Cr, F, I, As(?), Br(?), Sn(?).

It needs to be emphasized that the elements are not equally distributed in a living system. For example, an average human adult contains^{18,36} Na and K in about equal amounts, i.e. 100 g and 140 g, respectively, yet the plasma concentration of Na⁺ is 141 mM and that of K⁺ only 4 mM. Or to give a different example^{18,36}, there are about 4.2 g Fe, but only 72 mg Cu in a human body, but the plasma concentration is rather similar, namely, 20 μ M in iron and 18 μ M in copper. It is evident that complicated metabolic processes must be responsible for this compartmentalization, which also occurs in cells³⁷.

A deficiency in one of these elements will affect the wellbeing³⁵. For example, a deficiency in iron leads to anemia and a disorder of the immune system, or, a deficiency in zinc gives rise to skin lesions, impaired wound healing and growth retardation. Recognition of such effects plus the fact that an excess can be toxic (see Fig. 3) has led governmental institutions, like the U.S. Food and Drug Administration or the World Health Organization (WHO), to propose

Fig. 3. Biological response dependence on tissue concentration of an essential nutrient (solid curve) and of a deleterious substance (dashed curve). The relative position of the two curves on the concentration axis is arbitrary and one of convenience. Adapted from Ref. 14 with the permission of the author, Prof. Dr. R. Bruce Martin (University of Virginia, Charlottesville) and the publisher, Marcel Dekker, Inc. (New York).

so-called recommended Daily Allowances for adults, like 1–2 g sodium, 0.8 g of calcium, 10–20 mg of iron, 15 mg of zinc or 0.1 mg of chromium^{18,36}. Certainly, such values are subject to change with new insights being gained.

At the same time it needs to be pointed out that the biological response even to essential metals can be deleterious if given in excess; this is the reason why next to the mentioned 'Daily Allowances' also so-called 'Acceptable Daily Intake' (ADI) values (defined in mg/kg body weight) are recommended by the WHO³⁶, especially if harmful metals are considered. The biological response toward essential nutrients and deleterious substances is illustrated in Fig. 3. However, it needs to be emphasized that the biological response depends on the sex as well as on the age; there is a difference if children or adults are considered³⁶. In a given case the situation may be further complicated by synergistic or antagonistic effects with other compounds.

A further point one has to be aware of and which deserves emphasis is the fact that in the last 30–40 years methodology and physicochemical methods have improved tremendously and this is reflected in the values and conclusions given in the literature. A nice example of this is the 'history' of urease. Urease was the first enzyme ever to be crystallized and this was the proof that enzymes are well defined compounds and not some undefined mixtures. This achievement by Sumner in 1926 earned him the Nobel Prize in Chemistry (together with Kunitz and Northrup) 20 years later. It is interesting that Sumner³⁸ reported that his preparation of urease is devoid of metals; i.e. he had searched for these but the instrumentation available to him was not sensitive enough. Nearly 50 years later, i.e. in 1975, Zerner, Blakeley and colleagues^{39,40} showed that jack bean urease

(MW per subunit about 100000) contains two nickel ions (AW about 60)⁴⁰. Another 20 years later Karplus, Hausinger and colleagues⁴¹ published the X-ray crystal structure of *Klebsiella aerogenes* urease⁴². At present at least 5 different nickel-dependent enzymes are known^{42,43} (and this in contrast to the once believed claim that nickel enzymes do not exist) and among these is methyl-coenzyme M reductase, the enzyme responsible for the microbial formation of methane⁴³.

Some insights in metal ion-dependent reactivity patterns at the molecular level

As an example for a short excursion to the molecular level adenosine 5'-triphosphate (ATP⁴⁻) is a suitable molecule; it is very versatile, sits at the center of metabolism and is involved, either directly or indirectly through other nucleoside triphosphates, not only in biosynthesis but also in a vast majority of cellular activities^{35,44}. The role of ATP is so central that the rate at which it is formed is (in most cells) determined by the rate at which it is needed as a substrate for cytoplasmic or membrane-associated enzymes. It is held in steady state and it can be calculated that an average person will make an amount of ATP equivalent to the body weight in one day, and of course, the same amount is used in cellular activities⁴⁴.

However, it is often forgotten that ATP enters as substrate in enzymatic reactions in the form of complexes³⁵, very often as Mg(ATP)²⁻, and it is the mode of metal ion coordination which determines the way it reacts⁴⁵. For example, based on kinetic measurements it was concluded in the early eighties⁴⁶ that for an efficient transphosphorylation reaction two metal ions should be coordinated to the triphosphate chain, namely, one to the α,β -phosphate group and the other to the terminal γ -group⁴⁷. This view was confirmed in 1997 by an X-ray structure analysis⁴⁸ of *Escherichia coli* phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase where it was shown that indeed two metal ions are positioned, with the help of protein amino acid side-chains, such that an M(α,β)-M(γ) binding mode of ATP results.

In the context of the mentioned kinetic studies^{46,47} it had further been concluded that the two metal ions may bind to the triphosphate chain not only in the above mentioned mode but that an M(α)-M(β,γ) coordination can also be enforced with an enzyme and that this will lead to a reactive species ready for the transfer of a nucleoside monophosphate unit (or of a diphosphate group), a reaction occurring with nucleic acid polymerases. Indeed, this has also been confirmed 10 years later by X-ray crystal structure studies and mechanisms closely related to the mentioned binding mode have been proposed^{49,50}.

With the results summarized above in mind it is interesting that 9-[2-(phosphonmethoxy)ethyl]adenine (PMEA²⁻), which can be considered as an analog of (2'-deoxy)adenosine 5'-monophosphate ((d)AMP²⁻), shows antiviral properties against a variety of DNA viruses and retroviruses including human immunodeficiency viruses (HIV)^{51,52}. PMEa in its diphosphorylated form, PMEApp⁴⁻, now an analog of 2'-deoxyATP⁴⁻, is recognized by DNA polymerases as a substrate and thus incorporated into the growing nucleic acid chain which is then terminated due to the lack of a 3'-hydroxy group⁵³. Surprisingly, PMEApp⁴⁻ is for several DNA polymerases even a better substrate⁵³ than the parent nucleotide dATP⁴⁻. Why? Detailed studies of the coordinating properties of PMEa²⁻, which were possible only after much accumulated experience with nucleotides⁵⁴⁻⁶³, revealed that the ether oxygen of the -CH₂CH₂-O-CH₂-PO₃²⁻ chain, compulsory for a biological activity⁶⁴, participates in metal ion binding by giving rise to the formation of a 5-membered chelate of the phosphonate-bound metal ion⁶⁵⁻⁷⁰. This together with the higher basicity of the phosphonate group^{71,72}, compared to that of a phosphate group, facilitates M(α) binding in M₂(PMEApp)^{73,74}. Such a facilitated M(α) binding does not exist in M₂(dATP). Naturally, the facilitated M(α)-bind-

Fig. 4. Simplified structures of the M₂(dATP) and M₂(PMEApp) intermediates ready for the attack of a nucleophile (N) and on their way to the transition state in nucleic acid polymerases^{73,74}. Both metal ions (often Mg²⁺)^{49,50} are anchored^{46,47} to amino acid side-chains (often carboxylate groups of aspartate or glutamate units)^{49,50} of the enzyme. The nucleophile N may in addition interact with the M²⁺ at P(α) and the adenine moiety may be replaced by any other nucleobase residue. Adapted from Refs. 73 and 74.

ing mode will also facilitate a nucleophilic attack at P(α) as is depicted in Fig. 4 and in this way the higher reactivity of PMEApp⁴⁻, compared to dATP⁴⁻, in the DNA polymerase reaction can be rationalized⁷⁴. It may be added that also RNA polymerases⁷⁵ depend on the presence of metal ions as does telomerase, an unusual enzyme that contains an essential RNA subunit as well as protein components⁷⁶; this enzyme replicates the ends of linear chromosomes, also found in human cells. Similarly, the role of metal ions in the actions of ribozymes is now well recognized^{77,78}.

A general lesson follows from the above : The crucial kinetic experiments revealing the importance of the metal ion-binding mode to the triphosphate chain of a nucleoside 5'-triphosphate, i.e. M(α,β)-M(γ) versus M(α)-M(β,γ), for the kind of reaction that is taking place and which have allowed now to rationalize the properties of PMEApp⁴⁻ as a substrate for DNA polymerases, have been made in the early eighties⁴⁶, and before^{79,80}; this means, before the first report mentioning the antiviral properties of PMEApp⁴⁻ appeared in 1986⁸¹. In fact, the synthesis of PMEApp⁴⁻ was published⁸² only in 1987. However, only now these studies have implications for devising new antiviral agents⁷⁴. This demonstrates nicely that the 'usefulness' of a certain kind of (basic) research can not be predicted and known in advance as certain politicians claim in favoring so-called applied research.

Fine-tuning of metal ion properties via the coordination sphere

To get at least a superficial impression about the influence of the 'microenvironment', i.e. the inner part of the coordination sphere as well as outer-sphere effects, on the properties of metal ions, we shall concentrate on iron as an example⁸³. As said above, iron is the fourth most abundant element in the Earth's crust and, after aluminum, the second most abundant metal. Thus, when the Earth was young and life appeared (ca. 4200 m years ago), the atmosphere was benignly anaerobic and iron-dependent organisms met no difficulty in satisfying their needs. However, on a bright day (ca. 3500 m years ago) when blue-green algae (cyanobacteria) started to synthesize chlorophyll to capture the energy of the sunlight, problems began⁸⁴. With the appearance of dioxygen in the atmosphere due to photosynthesis, ferrous iron (Fe²⁺) was oxidized to ferric iron (Fe³⁺) and this is extremely poorly soluble in water at neutral pH and ambient conditions.

Since most living systems require iron for their growth and development, organisms had to devise strategies to solubilize and acquire this essential metal⁸³. Yet, iron is not only difficult to acquire, it must constantly be 'disciplined', monitored and appropriately shielded when stored⁸⁵. The

versatility of iron in biological electron transfer reactions, that is, the easy one-electron interconvertibility (Fe²⁺ \rightleftharpoons Fe³⁺ + e⁻), also enables the generation of oxygen-derived radicals and these most reactive species pose a threat to cells⁸⁴⁻⁸⁷. Considering this, it is amazing to observe that, depending on its 'microenvironment' (and oxidation state), iron is able to activate small molecules but also to protect and transport others which are very reactive⁸⁶.

That the 'microenvironment' has a significant influence on the properties of a metal ion can nicely be demonstrated visibly with cobalt, which neighbors iron in the Periodic Table. If one dissolves CoCl₂ once in water and once in ethanol, one obtains pink and blue solutions, respectively. This difference in color originates simply from the different solvation properties of water and ethanol towards Co²⁺. Addition of water to the ethanolic solution turns the color from blue to pink because H₂O is binding more strongly to Co²⁺ than is CH₃CH₂OH; to say it differently, the water molecules push ethanol out of the coordination sphere of the metal ion.

The excellent catalytic properties of heme-iron can be demonstrated if one takes a few milliliters of blood of a horse or pig, dilutes it with some water to make it more fluid and adds a few milliliters of hydrogen peroxide⁸⁸. H₂O₂ enters the coordination sphere by replacing H₂O in the sixth position (at the fifth is the phenolate-oxygen of a tyrosine residue)⁸⁹ of the heme-iron(III) in catalase to give the Fe(IV)=O and the porphyrin π cation radical intermediates⁸⁹; the enzyme is present in the blood⁸⁸ and decomposes the hydrogen peroxide immediately according to reaction (1),

to dioxygen and water and the vessel, in which the reaction is carried out, is promptly filled with a white/red foam⁸⁸. This foam, similar to egg white beaten with air, is created by the proteins present in the blood through the formation of dioxygen.

In contrast to the above example, where the heme-iron acting as a catalyst initiates an exceedingly fast reaction with a small molecule, H₂O₂, the same iron(III) unit in a different environment is able to protect and to transport (i.e. to reversibly bind) a highly reactive molecule, like nitrogen monoxide (nitric oxide, NO) as indicated further below. The high reactivity of the colorless NO radical becomes evident if it is exposed to air; then reaction (2),

takes place and the brown colored nitrogen dioxide is immediately formed.

Previously, nitrogen monoxide has generally been regarded as a common environmental toxin and pollutant, e.g. being a constituent of both, cigarette smoke and car exhaust emissions⁹⁰. Though this is true, of course, we know since the late eighties that this simple diatomic molecule also is an ubiquitous biological messenger⁹⁰. It functions, for example, as a cardiovascular agent, an effector molecule in the immune system, or as a neurotransmitter in the central and peripheral nervous system^{91,92}. NO can be produced by reduction of nitrite or oxidation of ammonia by some microbes. In mammals, nitric oxide synthase (NOS), also a heme enzyme, catalyzes the formation of NO from L-arginine^{91,92}.

A further intriguing example, which brings us back to iron, concerns the blood-sucking 'Kissing Bug', *Rhodnius prolixus*, an insect which has in its saliva a nitrovasodilator to assure sufficient blood meals. This nitrovasodilator is a unique heme-based protein, named nitrophorin^{93,94}, with the iron in the Fe^{III} (ferric) state and an imidazole nitrogen from a histidyl residue in one of the apical positions, the other being available for NO binding. This nitrophorin acts as a storage and delivery system for NO to the victim while feeding, resulting in vasodilation and inhibition of platelet aggregation. In response to the wound, the host releases histamine to induce wound healing. However, the nitrophorin captures and binds the histamine to its Fe^{III} and slows down in this way the defense mechanism of the host⁹⁴. X-Ray structure determinations confirmed that NO and histamine compete for the same binding site and become buried in the protein upon binding^{93,94}. The exchange is triggered by a change in pH, which is approximately 5 in the salivary gland and changes to about 7.4 in the host tissue which leads to the release of NO and the binding of histamine⁹⁴. An intriguing cascade of events! This example makes also understandable why there are efforts based on complex formations to produce therapeutic agents^{90,95} that release or bind NO.

The indicated properties of iron bring to mind the stanza entitled COLD IRON :

"Gold is for the mistress – silver for the maid –

Copper for the craftsman cunning at his trade."

"Good!" said the Baron, sitting in his hall,

"But Iron – Cold Iron – is master of them all."

Certainly, Rudyard J. Kipling (*30 December 1865, Mumbai; †18 January 1936, London), in the person of the Baron, is talking here of weapons made of iron, but we are inclined to continue by saying :

"Yes, Ladies and Gentlemen, Iron is quite able,

Yet, COMPLEXED Iron is unbeatable!!"

In conclusion

It is our hope that this short aphoristic account convinced you, the reader, that the following statement of Wood⁹⁶, made 25 years ago, contains some truth :

"If you think that Biochemistry is the Organic Chemistry of living systems, then you are misled;

BIOCHEMISTRY IS THE COORDINATION CHEMISTRY OF LIVING SYSTEMS."

Indeed, this statement is in so far history as the field of 'Bioinorganic Chemistry' or 'Biological Inorganic Chemistry' as it is also called is out of its infancy by now. It is an interdisciplinary field of science which is built on the strengths of Inorganic Chemistry and the Biological Sciences⁹⁷ and which requires the application of advanced physical and theoretical methodologies. Clearly, it encompasses and affects also the Environmental Sciences, Toxicology, and the Pharmaceutical Sciences as we have seen.

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